

EBFMC25-OP-62 · The Relationship Between Polypharmacy and Malnutrition Risk in Patients Receiving Home Health Care

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Multiple medication use, also known as polypharmacy, has significantly increased over the past 20 years, especially among individuals requiring care (Bardel, Wallander, and Svärdsudd, 2000; Charlesworth, 2015). This study aims to examine the relationship between polypharmacy and malnutrition risk in patients receiving home health care.

Materials and Methods: For this cross-sectional study, data from patients aged 18 years and older registered in the Home Health Care unit of a secondary-level state hospital were retrospectively analyzed between February and March 2025. Patient data including age, sex, total duration of home health care enrollment (in months), use of medical devices, number of chronic diseases, and number of medications used were obtained from medical records. Polypharmacy was defined as the simultaneous use of five or more medications (Mair, 2019). In addition, the following clinically validated assessment tools evaluated by trained physicians were extracted from patient files: Mini Nutritional Assessment-Short Form (MNA-SF), Katz Index of Activities of Daily Living, Clinical Frailty Scale, and Braden Pressure Ulcer Risk Assessment Scale (Bergstrom, Braden, Laguzza, and Holman, 1987; Guigoz, Vellas, and Garry, 1996; Pehlivanoglu, Özkan, Balcioğlu, Bilge, and Unluoglu, 2018; Theou, et al., 2018). For medical device use, the presence of percutaneous endoscopic gastrostomy (PEG), colostomy, nasogastric tube, urinary catheter, mechanical ventilator, and oxygen concentrator was evaluated.

Results: This study included data from a total of 72 patients. The median number of medications used was 6 [IQR: 4]. Polypharmacy was present in 53 patients (73.6%). The median MNA-SF score was 11 [IQR: 2]. According to the MNASF, 10 patients (13.9%) had malnutrition, 36 (50.0%) were at risk of malnutrition, and

22 (36.1%) had no malnutrition. The MNA-SF score was positively correlated with the Katz Index and Braden Scale scores ($r=0.333$ and 0.466 , respectively; $p=0.004$ and <0.001). MNA-SF scores were negatively correlated with the number of chronic diseases and the number of medications used ($r=-0.384$ and -0.499 , respectively; $p=0.001$ and <0.001). No significant association was found between MNA-SF scores and age, sex, total duration of home health care enrollment, medical device use, or Clinical Frailty Scale scores ($p\geq 0.05$). According to regression analysis, the number of medications used, and the Braden Scale score were significant predictors of the MNA-SF score ($p<0.001$, $R^2=0.475$).

Conclusion: According to our study, as the number of medications increases in patients receiving home health care, the risk of malnutrition also increases. A decrease in Braden Scale score contributes to the development of malnutrition.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Elderly patients, home health care, malnutrition, nutritional assessment, polypharmacy

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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